

Studies on hydrodynamics of annular circulating fluidised bed drier with millet ragi particles mixture

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Millet and ragi particles mixture with the millet particles having average diameter $2250 \mu\text{m}$ and density 1163.9 kg m^{-3} and ragi particles of average diameter $1500 \mu\text{m}$ and density 1310.4 kg m^{-3} , with the mass fraction 0.5 each of millet and particles were used to study the hydrodynamics of an annular circulating fluidised bed drier. Gap openings were varied from 12 mm to 72 mm and it was found that mass flux of solids remained constant for all air rates for gap openings greater than 60 mm. Dilute phase flow and dense phase slugging flow regime models were verified. A correction factor, K has been incorporated for the dense slugging flow regime. The error in the use of the model for pressure drop calculation was 28%. As there was smooth flow of particle mixture and little variation in pressure drop in dilute phase regime, drying could be done in this regime.

Food processing and preservation is one of the important areas where research is being vigorously pursued in many agro based countries. Drying using fluidised bed finds very wide applications because of several advantages such as high degree of contact between gas and solids, very high heat and mass transfer rates, better temperature control, absence of moving parts and good mixing over other driers. The hydrodynamic behavior of fluidised bed driers has been well established and relations are available for a variety of materials. However, in a fluidised bed, the product material has to be separated using a cyclone separator. The product from the cyclone can be recirculated if necessary. The annular circulating fluidised bed drier (ACFBD) is a unit which can be thought of as a fluidised bed drier with a built in separator and recirculator. The use of ACFBD in recent years is picking up and is being used for drying many granular food particles. The other salient features of ACFBD are requirement of less space, low pressure drop, and lower risk of food grains being roasted or charred.

We reported earlier^{1,2} the hydrodynamics of the ACFBD with ragi and sand particles. The characterizations of various regimes such as dilute phase and slugging flow phase were discussed. The present communication reports the hydrodynamics of ACFBD with millet ragi particles mixture with the mass fraction of 0.5 each.

Results and discussion

During experimentation for the air velocity between 1.411 to 1.764 m s^{-1} , erratic flow of solids and fluctuation of pressure drop was observed indicating slugging dense

flow. For the air velocity between 1.746 and 2.115 m s^{-1} the gradual reduction in magnitude of erratic flow of grain particle and fluctuation of pressure drop was observed indicating transitions regime. For the air velocity above 2.115 m s^{-1} smooth flow of particles and less fluctuations in pressure drop was observed indicating dilute phase flow regime. This regime transition classification was based on methods and observation suggested by Leung and Robert³. Fig. 1 shows the variation of mass flux of solids with gap opening

Fig. 1. Plot mass flux of solids vs gap opening : (\diamond) 1.411, (\blacksquare) 1.587, (\triangle) 1.764, (\blacklozenge) 2.116, ($*$) 2.469, (\circ) 2.822, (\blacktriangle) 3.175, ($+$) 3.527, (\square) 3.704, (\times) 4.056, (\bullet) 4.233 and (Δ) 4.409 m s^{-1} .

for the two flow regimes. The data was fitted to eq. (1) by regression analysis,

$$G_s = (1300 U_o - 3322) X - 110 \quad (1)$$

with an average absolute deviation of 10% (Fig. 1). It is seen from Fig. 1 that for both regimes, the mass flux of solids increases with gap opening up to 60 mm and thereafter remains constant; for a specific gap opening, the mass flux increases with air velocity. However in the dilute flow regime, the increase in mass flux of solids for velocities greater than 4.05 m s^{-1} is negligible. Thus gap openings of 60 mm and an air velocity of 4.05 m s^{-1} limits the capacity of this set-up for handling solids.

Fig. 2. G_s , Experimental vs G_s , calculated : (\square) 1.411, (\blacklozenge) 1.587, (\times) 1.764, ($*$) 2.116, (\blacktriangle) 2.469, ($+$) 2.822, ($-$) 3.175, (\triangle) 3.527, (\circ) 3.704, (\blacksquare) 4.056, (\circ) 4.233 and (Δ) 4.409 m s^{-1} .

The experimental and calculated values (eqs. 3–5) of pressure drop for dilute phase and slugging dense flow are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The maximum errors were regis-

Fig. 3. Pressure drop calculated using model equation vs experimental values : (\times) 2.116, (\circ) 2.469, (\square) 2.822, ($+$) 3.175, (\circ) 3.527, (Δ) 3.704, ($*$) 4.056, (\blacksquare) 4.233 and (Δ) 4.409 m s^{-1} .

Fig. 4. Pressure drop calculated using model equation vs experimental values without correction factor : (\diamond) 1.411, (\square) 1.587 and (Δ) 1.764 m s^{-1} .

tered to be 28% and 40% for dilute and slugging flow regimes respectively. The large error in the slugging flow regime was reduced by introduction of a suitable correction factor K , called erratic factor, to account for the erratic flow pattern in this regime. Thus eq. (3) was modified as

$$\Delta P = K \rho_s l (1 - \epsilon) g \quad (2)$$

where K was estimated by regression analysis as 0.7 for the particle mixture studied. Figs. 4 and 5 indicate the improvement in calculated values of pressure drop in the slugging flow regime with maximum error being 28%.

Fig. 5. Pressure drop calculated using model equation vs experimental values without correction factor : (\diamond) 1.411, (\square) 1.587 and (Δ) 1.764 m s^{-1} .

Conclusion : The position of the air distributor tube (gap opening) has a significant effect on the mass flux of solids

handled by the unit, the maximum mass flux of solids being for a gap opening of 60 mm. The hydrodynamic model proposed for pressure drop can be utilised in scale up studies. A new factor K has been introduced to account for the erratic flow of solids in the slugging flow regime. As there was smooth flow of particle mixture and little variation in pressure drop in dilute phase regime, drying could be done in this regime.

Models for pressure drop :

Mathematical model for pressure drop for the two regimes has been successfully tested for ragi and sand particles and discussed earlier^{1,2} are indicated below :

$$\Delta P = \rho_s l (1 - \epsilon)g \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta P = \Delta P_s + \Delta P_k + \Delta P_f \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta P_f = \Delta P_{fg} + \Delta P_{fs} \quad (5)$$

Eqs. 1 and 2 are for dilute phase and slugging flow regimes respectively. The same models are adopted in the present work. For millet and ragi particles mixture with the mass fraction of 0.5, slugging dense flow regime was observed for air velocity ranging from 1.41 to 1.76 m s⁻¹ and dilute phase flow regime was observed for air velocity ranging from 2.11 to 4.409 m s⁻¹ when the experiment was conducted.

Experimental

Fig. 6 gives the details of the experimental set up. It consisted of a central tube (fluidisation chamber) (diameter 0.015 m) where the solids were fluidised and an outer annular chamber (diameter 0.046 m) for recirculation of solids that deflected into it by the hemispherical dish. An air distributor was placed below the central tuber and the opening between the fluidisation chamber and the distributor (X) could be varied. This opening fixed the mass flux of solid into the fluidisation chamber. The position of the movable distributor and hence the opening was measured using a cathetometer. The overall height of the annular chamber including the hemispherical dish was 1.90 m.

Procedure : Uniformly sieved and cleaned millet particles of size 2250 μm, with the density 1163.9 kg m⁻³ and ragi particles of average diameter 1500 μm and density 1310.4 kg m⁻³ with the mass fraction of 0.5 each, were used to study the hydrodynamics. For gap openings ranging from 12 to 72 mm and air velocity from 1.41 to 4.41 m s⁻¹, the pressure drop was measured with a Rosemount differential pressure transducer. The mass rate of transport of millet-ragi particles mixture particles was determined by noting

Fig. 6. Experimental set up : (A) Outer tube, (B) inner gas tube (fluidisation chamber), (C) annular space, (D) hemispherical dish, (E) air exit, (F) air distributor tube, (G₁, G₂) pressure tapings, (H) compressor, (J) air filter, (K) rotameter, (k_k) particle movement observation section of length L and (L) feed inlet.

the time for their downward flow over a predetermined length in the annular chamber. The mass flux of solids, G_s was calculated using the relation,

$$G_s = W V_p / A_c L \quad (6)$$

Nomenclature

A_c = cross-sectional area of fluidisation chamber, m²

g = acceleration due to gravity, m s⁻²

G_s = mass flux of solids, kg m⁻², s

K = correction factor to account for erratic flow behaviour in the slugging flow regime, (-)

l = length of the fluidising section, m

L = length of the down flow particle observation section in the annular portion, m

U_o = superficial gas velocity, m s⁻¹

V_p = velocity of particle in the annular portion, m s⁻¹

W = mass of solid particle in the precalibrated annular portion, kg

X = gap opening, distance between the distributor and fluidisation chamber, m

ΔP = total pressure drop, pa

ΔP_f = pressure drop due to frictional resistance of gas solid mixture, pa

ΔP_{fg} = pressure drop for empty tube using fanning friction factor, pa

ΔP_{fs} = pressure drop due to frictional resistance of solid, pa

ΔP_k = pressure drop due to kinetic energy change of solids, pa

ΔP_s = pressure drop due to static head of solid, pas

ϵ = porosity of bed under fluidising condition, (-)

ρ_s = density of solid, kg m⁻³

References

1. P. Sivashanmugam and S. Sundaram, *Powder Techno.*, 1999, **103**, 165.
2. P. Sivashanmugam and S. Sundaram, *J. Powder Handling Processing*, 2000, **12**, 57.
3. L. S. Leung and J. W. Robert, *Ind. Eng. Chem Process Des. Dev.*, 1967, **15**, 3.